

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

9 & 10 September 2024 | Manchester

The
Alan Turing
Institute

Swansea
University
Prifysgol
Abertawe

Population Data Science
Gwyddor Data Poblogaeth

Focussing on the future:

How do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

The workshop logistics

The workshop was designed to provide members of the AIM community with an opportunity to discuss key topics shaping the future of AI and MLTC research, aiming to improve lives for those living with or caring for people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions. In collaboration with NIHR, six discussion topics with guiding questions were prepared to explore challenges and potential solutions.

The event welcomed 80-100 registered attendees, with 12-16 participants engaging in discussions on each topic and eight joining online. A one-hour session included 50 minutes for discussion, focusing on capturing attendees' insights and identifying three key takeaways for feedback.

There were 7 topics discussed in the workshop, this summary includes the discussion and takeaway from the 5th topic.

- **Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?**
- **Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**
- **Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?**
- **Topic 4: What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?**
- **Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?**
- **Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?**
- **Topic 7: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**

Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?

Chaired and Scribed by: Reece Labrom & Mon Fletcher

The key takeaways

1. We need to help the public understand how AI impacts their lives and health conditions, giving them the tools to do so easily. This can help build trust and understanding of AI and lead to wider acceptance and understanding of how it relates to their own health needs.
2. Academic collaborations are important and enabling open access to developments will help drive change and improvement.
3. Partnerships with the government and key NHS stakeholders, such as clinicians and managers, can help enable AI acceptance and help garner public support and trust. Additionally, making a push to engage underrepresented stakeholders, such as social care and local authorities, into the conversation will help facilitate understanding for a wider audience.

Recommendations for MLTC funders

4. Establish a strategic communications framework:
 - Fund development of accessible, jargon-free communications about AI in healthcare
 - Support the creation of a bank of success stories and case studies linked to centralised space, rather than scattering in different websites,
 - Resource PPIE involvement in messaging and terminology decisions
 - Develop targeted communication strategies for different stakeholder groups
5. Create a collaborative implementation network:
 - Fund consortium-wide coordination of implementation efforts
 - Support development of shared evaluation frameworks
 - Resource partnerships with NHS trusts and local authorities
 - Enable pilot studies in prevention and diagnostics
 - Fund equity impact assessments of AI implementations
 - Support engagement with underrepresented stakeholders, particularly in social care
 - Create mechanisms for sharing learning across projects and regions

Summary of all the discussion

- The majority of stakeholders were already present on brief so we decided to look at what would success look like and work backwards
- Important from a public point of view - selling AI and removing the scary stigma around it, success would be identifying easy successes that we can publicise and improve the image. We've all heard of the negative stories, this has led to the people we want to engage with becoming wary and making it harder to get the public involved.
- Challenging the above point, is understanding AI is important or is the project's outputs aiding healthcare and the NHS more important?
- We can identify a whole new range of patients who are unaware of their conditions, this could make them aware and seek medical guidance/help which could in turn cause more strain on an already burdened NHS system - This could be turned on its head by using as a positive AI story by helping identify and aid people that would have a significant medical problem in the future.
- Positive news stories are key to improving AI perception.
- AI - use of the word artificial - conjures the idea of 'false'
- AI isn't a solution for all problems, but it can shorten the work and make it easier. AI can help to inform and better prepare people for problems to come.
- People want to see concrete tangible impact, society wants instant results. If AI can help resolve waiting list issues, enable more screening, and open up local community hubs. We can shorten diagnostic timelines and help prevent unnecessary harm to individuals caused by waiting.
- How do we use AI to help with the burden in the NHS? How can AI be part of a solution? Winter pressures - something tangible for the public. AI doesn't need to be at the forefront but mention can be useful.
- Information is already readily available, so why not use this to improve the current situation?
- Patients don't need to know the ins and outs of everything but being made aware that their doctors and GPs are using these tools can help reassure them. How do we tow the line between informative and understandable?
- Narrative is important and needs to be meaningful to patients. Needs to be relevant to people.
- Artificial Intelligence - terminology may need tweaking. Language around tools can change opinions of technology. PPIE is key to deciding this.
- Before reaching out to stakeholders, you have to decide 'what' is being disseminated.
- What? Then, Who? Then, How?
- AI is a methodology/tool to enable change.
- Learn lessons from 1st dissemination and improve the process.

- We need to be part of the solution and to be involved in that we need a key and common mission that all stakeholders have bought into.
- 2 key areas that can be focused on - prevention and diagnostics.
- Still in the exploratory stage of research. Many AIM projects are proof of concept. They are all long-term. AIM was testing AI as a methodology to look at MLTCs
- Need to be careful not to cause new or enhance existing inequalities due to incomplete or missing data. Is it the right populations, the right data? Is there bias? Are the definitions strict enough?
- AIM projects are very varied and trying to link these together will allow us to see if we can work as a group to have a consistent message.
- AIM RSF/PIs need to work together to decide how to make their own plans more reflective of the entire consortium, which can help drive progress for all. Need to demonstrate that our concepts work before engaging wider communities such as the government and NHS. Having a united voice lends more weight to what we're saying and creates mass momentum.